

DAMAGE DEVELOPMENT IN PLAIN WEAVE GFRP

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SUMMARY: Damage development in a two layer plain weave glass/epoxy system under quasi-static loading has been investigated. The damage comprised matrix cracking and delamination. Three distinct types of damage morphology were found and were related to the relative shift of the fabric laminae with respect to each other. The tortuous path of the transverse cracking and repeat of damage patterns were found to depend upon tow and weave characteristics, respectively.

KEYWORDS: plain weave, GFRP, damage development, lamina shift.

INTRODUCTION

Over recent years there has been a renewed interest in woven composite materials. Although woven composites exhibit slightly (approximately 5-10 %) lower moduli and strength than equivalent cross-ply laminates they offer some specific advantages. They have very good drapability, especially the common eight harness satin weave. Manufacturing costs can be reduced as one layer of cloth replaces two unidirectional plies, resulting in easier handling and shorter lay-up times. They also have better impact resistance as the nature of the weave localises the damage.

The theoretical modelling of the elastic behaviour of woven fabric composite materials is now well developed. This includes both closed form analytical models building on the early research of Chou and co-workers, e.g. [1], and finite element methods such as those of Whitcomb [2]. However, due to the nature of the fibre architecture and the associated complex damage morphology, work concerned with characterising and predicting damage onset and growth, together with the effect of damage on residual properties, is more limited. Present models require extensive computational effort and involve many simplifications, e.g. [3]. The aim of the present work is to address these issues making use of a model (transparent) GFRP system in order to facilitate damage observation.

Marsden et al. [4-6] characterised the damage in an eight harness satin weave glass/epoxy composite under both quasi-static and fatigue loading. Damage development was found to be a function of tow and weave architecture. It is clear from the work of Marsden et al. [4-6] and Boniface et al. [7] that cracking damage in woven GFRP and CFRP has a complex morphology and that this morphology needs to be understood before the effect of damage can be modelled. The present paper studies the damage initiation and development in a plain weave glass/epoxy composite.

In the present work a laminate assembled from two layers of plain weave fabric was used. A particular feature of interest has been the effect of the shift of the fabric layers relative to one another on the damage pattern which develops. The effect of this shift on material properties has been considered analytically by other workers. The models of Naik and Shembekar [8] report

optimum elastic properties for configurations out of phase with one another, i.e. fabric layers shifted relative to each other. Yurgartis and Maurer [9] suggest that relative lamina shift, along with weave configuration and stacking sequence, influence interlaminar shear strength.

MATERIALS AND EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

The reinforcement used was an E-glass plain weave fabric with similar warp and weft tows consisting of three finer bundles twisted together (Fig. 1). The cloth has a weight of 182 g/m² and thickness of 0.15 mm. It was marginally unbalanced with 142 and 126 tow ends in the warp and weft directions, respectively. The matrix used was an Epikote 828 epoxy resin with an NMA curing agent and Ancamine K61B accelerator. Laminates were fabricated using a two layer wet lay up process, in which resin was introduced into cloths which had been carefully marked out to ensure alignment and stacked so as to maintain overall maintain symmetry about the mid-plane. The laminates were cured at 100°C for 3 hours and post-cured at 150°C for a further 3 hours.

Figure 1. SEM photomicrograph of plain weave cloth

Test coupons (20 mm x 200 mm) were cut using a water cooled diamond saw. Aluminium end tags of dimensions 20 mm x 50 mm were bonded to the coupons leaving a 100 mm gauge length at the centre of which were bonded strain gauges. Quasi-static mechanical testing was performed using an Instron 1175 machine at a crosshead speed of 0.5 mm/min. Data was recorded using a PC-based data-logger package. A linear regression analysis of the stress-strain curve between 1000 and 4000 microstrain was carried out to obtain moduli data.

Observations of damage accumulation were facilitated by the transparent nature of the GFRP, which allowed the plan view damage development to be observed by in situ photography. Samples were unclamped from the grips of the testing machine prior to being photographed. Polishing longitudinal edge sections allows the through thickness profile of the damage to be studied, following the method of Marsden et al. [6]. With accurate measurements during sample preparation, a plan view array of cracks may be located and viewed in cross section.

RESULTS

Laminate Properties

Laminate properties are given in Table 1. The number in brackets denotes the number of samples tested. Crack initiation and failure strains are comparable to those found by Marsden et al. [6] on a similar eight harness satin material. The relatively low volume fraction of 36 % is attributed to the open nature of the weave and low pressure used in fabrication. The variation in modulus is largely attributable to local variations in laminate thickness due to nesting and the thin nature of the cloth.

Table 1: Laminate properties

E_0 (GPa)	18.7 ± 1.4 (12)
σ_{TS} (MPa)	260
ϵ_i (%)	0.6
ϵ_f (%)	2.1
V_f (%)	36
Thickness (mm)	~0.4

Damage Development

Under quasi-static loading short transverse cracks of approximately 1 mm in length initiate in the weft tows at an initiation strain, ϵ_i , of approximately 0.6 %. Photographs of edge sections show the initial damage occurs near the tow centre (Fig.2a). The crack path is often complicated and is diverted at the interfaces of the three twisted bundles within each tow. At higher levels of strain further cracking initiates towards the tow ends (Fig 2b). The damage tends to saturate, resulting in a reasonably regular spacing within the tows of approximately twice the tow thickness (Fig.2c). The damage is confined to the tows and does not extend into the matrix.

Plan view photomicrographs show that the transverse cracking is aligned at approximately 5 - 10° to the horizontal weft tows which is a result of the cracks following the line of the twist within the tows. The average crack length at saturation is roughly equivalent to the inter-crimp distance which is much less than the laminate width.

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 2: Polished edge section photomicrographs of damage at (a) 1.0 % strain, (b) 1.2 % strain and (c) 1.6 % strain.

Interestingly, there are three types of damage morphology that may be found in any one laminate. The use of edge sections to study the local relative position of the cloths has shown the morphologies to be as follows.

Banded transverse cracking in weft tows.

The plan view here shows damage to be contained in horizontal bands, perpendicular to the loading direction, P, which are composed of transverse cracks in the weft tows (Fig 3a). The loading direction indicated applies to parts (a), (b) and (c) of the figure. This damage morphology occurs when the two cloths lie in phase with one another as shown in Fig. 3b and indicated schematically in Fig. 3c. The two weft tows are superimposed resulting in damage free resin rich bands.

Figure 3: Damage morphology of case A, (a) plan view photomicrograph, (b) polished edge section photomicrograph and (c) schematic representation of edge section

Banded transverse cracking in weft tows with a regular array of delaminations.

In this damage morphology the plan view damage is similar to case A but with additional delaminations orientated in the loading direction (Fig. 4a). These delaminations initiate at approximately 1.5 % strain. In this case the two cloths are symmetrical about the mid-plane, i.e. 180° out of phase (Fig. 4b and Fig. 4c) and the transverse cracking is arranged in bands as in case A. The delaminations occur at sites where two warp tows touch, i.e. every 180°. This leads to a delamination at every other warp / weft cross over point. The delaminations are dependent on laminate consolidation and are found only if the warp tows are touching.

(a) ← P →

(b)

(c)

Figure 4: Damage morphology of case B, (a) plan view photomicrograph, (b) polished edge section photomicrograph and (c) schematic representation of edge section

Regularly distributed plan view transverse cracking in weft tows.

This is shown in plan view in Figure 5a and results when the cloths are at some intermediate phase between the above two cases (Fig. 5b and Fig.5c). The adjacent weft tows are no longer superimposed and overlap when viewed in plan view, resulting in no through-thickness resin rich regions.

(a) ← P →

(b)

(c)

Figure 5: Damage morphology of case C, (a) plan view photomicrograph, (b) polished edge section photomicrograph and (c) schematic representation of edge section

Similarities in cracking morphology can be found for all three cases. Transverse cracking appears to be more pronounced at cross over points between the warp and weft tows. This can clearly be seen in both cases A and B. Delaminations may be found in cases A and C at high damage densities, although the delaminations do not appear with the regularity seen in case B. Such a delamination is shown in Figure 3b, located at the interface of a warp and weft tow. Of the three crack morphologies the banded plan view damage morphology (case A) was found to be dominant, suggesting that the open nature of the plain weave cloth encourages nesting of the cloths on one another during consolidation.

In this study it has been shown that the relative shift of adjacent cloths influences damage morphology, in addition to the previously reported influence on mechanical properties [4-5]. These findings should be considered in any subsequent detailed modelling of the effect of damage development on mechanical properties of woven composite materials.

CONCLUSIONS

The damage morphology seen in a plain weave GFRP laminate under quasi-static loading was found to be dependent on tow characteristics, weave geometry and relative cloth shift. The transverse cracking morphology, both plan view and through thickness, was strongly influenced by the twist of individual tows, whilst the macroscopic cracking patterns were determined by the weave geometry and relative cloth shift. A regular array of delaminations between fabric layers was found to result for relative cloth shifts of 180° , when the laminate was symmetrical about its mid-plane. Transverse cracking initiated near the tow centre and, at saturation, developed a reasonably regular saturation spacing within the tows of approximately twice the tow thickness.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors would like to thank Reg Whattingham for his technical assistance and also Rolls-Royce plc and the EPSRC for funding a CASE studentship for C. Manger.

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